

2025

Summative Evaluation

End of Program Evaluation Report
RADx-UP Tracking & Evaluation Team &
Operations Team

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Abbreviations

CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
EO	Evaluation Objective
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
MSC	Most Significant Change
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

This summative report details key evaluation findings from the Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics in Underserved Community (RADx-UP) Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2). Specifically, it presents findings across five evaluation objectives:

- 1) Describe the success of the grant application and utilization processes;
- 2) Evaluate awardees' satisfaction with CDCC administration and support activities;
- 3) Evaluate RP2 program reach and diversity;
- 4) Evaluate testing and enrollment outcomes;
- 5) Evaluate the potential translational science impacts of the program.

The data presented were collected between January 2022, or the start of evaluation activities, through December 2024. Data collection activities included a review of administrative records from program governing bodies and project surveys conducted throughout and beyond the project lifecycle. Surveys collected both quantitative measures and qualitative measures that were used to gauge program impact within domains of the Translational Science Benefit Model.

Key Findings from Evaluation

- The CDCC has funded **25 RP2 projects across seven funding cycles**. There was variability across funding cycles in the number of applicants, funding rate, and time from notice of award to project start-up.
- Awardees were **highly satisfied with the support provided from the administrative and governing bodies**.
- RP2 projects had reach across all NIH identified underserved and vulnerable populations. The most common underserved populations reached by the RP2 projects include **socioeconomically disadvantaged people, Black and Hispanic/Latino populations**, and **people living in rural areas**.
- RP2 projects generally did not reach their self-selected enrollment or testing targets, although sample sizes were not statistically determined. Not surprisingly, there was variability across projects in the ability to implement enrollment and testing, highlighting opportunities to derive successful strategies from projects that did exceed their targets. Overall, **4,086 participants were enrolled (34.6% of the target)**, and **4,948 COVID-19 tests were administered (25.1% of the target)**.
- Commonly reported challenges across cycles included **reporting testing results, administrative challenges**, and **testing reporting challenges**.
- Reflecting on their impacts and the changes to occur as a result of their work, RP2 projects commonly identified immediate impacts to **communities and public health** via increased access to testing and improved education. Impacts in the other domains of the Translational Science Benefit Model were less frequently reported due to the pilot stage nature of this program. The projects investment in scholarly dissemination,

including beyond the project period, may facilitate additional potential translational benefits not captured during the evaluation period.

Background

Overview of the RP2 Program.

The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) is part of the larger, National Institutes of Health (NIH) supported Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program, which aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality. The RADx-UP program seeks to achieve this primary aim by:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation.
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of US Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved.
- Strengthening the available data on population disparities in infection rates, disease progression, and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address inequities in COVID-19 diagnostics.

RP2 awards up to \$200,000 in direct costs for a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of implementing novel or emerging testing strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in underserved geographic locations.¹ Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding.¹

The RADx-UP RP2 Program Aims were:

- RP2 Aim 1: *Testing access*. To understand and address the barriers (language, literacy, technology access, etc) of underserved communities to accessing new diagnostic testing and novel testing strategies. A historic inequity in research is that underserved communities are often last at accessing new or innovative technologies, and vulnerable populations are often excluded in emerging technology development programs.
- RP2 Aim 2: *Emerging testing technologies*. Evaluate the feasibility of implementing emerging and novel COVID-19 testing technologies in underserved communities.

- RP2 Aim 3: *Pilot implementation*. Leverage the CDCC to expedite a research pilot program and to better understand the research infrastructure and administration required to rapidly deploy novel testing strategies to underserved populations.

RP2 projects are human subject research studies requiring review and approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB). IRB's must comply with HIPAA and other human subjects research requirements as described in FDA regulation 21 CFR 56. The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supported RP2 projects as they served their communities. The CDCC provided administrative and operational support systems and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The CDCC was a joint effort between the Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill. The CDCC partnered with a third-party evaluation team within UNC, Abacus Evaluation, to track and evaluate the RADx-UP initiative, referred to throughout as the Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team. Specifically, within the CDCC a Testing Core was established to provide technical and clinical expertise in support of the research projects and implementation of EUA-authorized diagnostic testing. Testing Core overall support involved the following services: utilize a protocol review process to evaluate key RADx-UP Project protocol and testing plan elements, perform project reviews and monitoring, provide expert communications and guidance, and provide robust procurement support. The Testing Core's Procurement group established direct connections to secure COVID-19 test kits and supplies at little to no cost to project teams. These procurement channels included RADx TECH Channel, DoD Channel, and direct channels with each vendor, which were particularly critical during periods of national supply chain shortages.

[Overview of the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation.](#)

The T&E team conducted a comprehensive mixed-methods evaluation of the RP2 program between January 2022 and December 2024. The evaluation objectives were designed to understand process, outcomes, and impacts of the program overall, including how the CDCC functioned to facilitate project implementation and how projects, in turn, enrolled participants, increased testing, and contributed to the translational evidence base in ways that benefited society. See [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#).

The RADx-UP RP2 Program Evaluation Objectives (EO) were:

1. E01: Describe the success of the grant application process and utilization process.
2. E02: Evaluate awardees' satisfaction with CDCC administration and support activities.
3. E03: Evaluate RP2 program reach and diversity.
4. E04: Evaluate testing and enrollment outcomes.
5. E05: Evaluate potential translational science benefit impacts of the program.²

A cross-walk of the RP2 aims and associated evaluation objectives is available in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. RADx-UP RP2 Program Evaluation Aims and Objectives

	E01 - Describe the success of the grant application process and utilization process	E02 - Evaluate awardees' satisfaction with CDCC administration and support activities.	E03 - RP2 program reach and diversity.	E04 - Evaluate testing and enrollment outcomes.	E05 – Evaluate the Potential Translational science benefit impacts of the program. ²
RP2 Aim 1: <i>Testing access</i>					
RP2 Aim 2: <i>Emerging testing technologies</i>					
RP2 Aim 3: <i>Pilot Implementation</i>					

The T&E team framed its evaluation by utilizing core components of the **Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**² and the **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework** (see [Figure 1](#)).^{3,4}

[Figure 1. RE-AIM Framework and TSBM Model Domains and Related Measures](#)

- The Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)**² is a framework designed to guide evaluation of the impact of research on society, outlining four core domains for the evaluation of clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits. The T&E team used TSBM to assess RP2's potential translational impacts through changes in clinical guidelines or practice, community or public health circumstances, policies, and economic conditions (see [Figure 2](#)). Potential benefits are impacts that might be expected with some degree of confidence.³ As RP2 funded pilot projects intended to generate information on implementation feasibility, this method was applied to gauge research teams' perspectives on eventual translational science benefits of the research, if proven feasible and further developed and funded.

The **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework** was applied, in complement to TSBM, to guide evaluation of the reach, adoption, implementation processes, and long-term effects of the RP2 program.^{4,5} RE-AIM was used to define the scope and select key constructs for evaluation, under the evaluation objectives.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)^{2,7} Guiding Impact Evaluation

<p>CLINICAL</p>	<p>Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)</p>
<p>COMMUNITY</p>	<p>Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)</p>
<p>ECONOMIC</p>	<p>Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)</p>
<p>POLICY</p>	<p>Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)</p>

Methods

Data Sources.

The RADx-UP RP2 evaluation used a longitudinal design which involved collecting data from RP2 program awardees at several timepoints. Projects were on a standard data collection cycle, that was sometimes extended in line with program timelines. Longitudinal data, including project progress updates, were presented over the course of the project to guide quality improvement efforts. For this summative report, data are presented cross-sectionally to reflect findings at the program level. For repeated measures, the most recent timepoint is presented. Data sources included RP2 program records, project intake surveys, bimonthly evaluation surveys, and a post-program follow-up survey administered six months after the project closeout date. [Table 2](#) provides an overview of data sources as related to evaluation objectives.

Table 2. RP2 Data Sources that Inform RP2 Evaluation Objectives

	RP2 Program Records	Project Intake Survey	Bimonthly Progress Surveys	Midpoint and Closeout Survey	Follow-Up Survey
E01 - Describe the success of the grant application process and utilization process					
E02 - Evaluate awardees' satisfaction with CDCC administration and support activities.					
E03 - Evaluate RP2 program reach and diversity.					
E04 - Evaluate testing and enrollment outcomes.					
E05 – Evaluate the translational science benefit impacts of the program. ²					

RP2 Program Records. The RP2 grant administration leadership team worked with the T&E team to provide grant administration data such as the number of applicants per cycle. These records map onto the reach domain of the RE-AIM framework to allow the team to better understand who the awardees were and how they engaged with the application process.

Project Intake Survey. The Project Intake Survey, completed by the project team at enrollment, collected data reflecting the demographic makeup of the populations in each project's catchment areas and characteristics of the project, also mapping to the RE-AIM reach domain.

Bimonthly Progress Surveys. RP2 projects completed bimonthly surveys with rolling data collection tied to their project start dates. These surveys assessed components of the RE-AIM framework. Reach and adoption indicators included the number and types of testing strategies used, implementation indicators included the types of community-driven strategies projects implemented, and maintenance indicators included the capacity of projects to sustain research activities.⁴ Each bimonthly survey collected information on project testing and enrollment; challenges faced in completing the program; protocol changes; progress towards meeting milestones; and achieved outcomes at that timepoint. It should be noted that these outcomes are potential benefits, rather than achieved benefits, as most projects lasted for a short period of time and realized impacts (i.e., changes in individual or population health) were out of the scope of this evaluation.

Midpoint and Closeout Survey. The midpoint surveys (6-month) and closeout surveys (12-month) contained additional questions to gather data on project outcomes as relates to TSBM domains, research productivity, including RADx-UP peer-reviewed publications and other scholarly products to understand how projects.

Follow-up Survey. The T&E team administered a follow-up survey six months after project completion to assess longer-term outcomes and impacts and maintenance of the pilot projects. This survey assessed any sustained project activities and other achievements from the pilot project (such as additional external funding, new partnerships, new publications, etc.). Items on this survey also assessed what projects viewed as the most significant change occurring as a result of their work across the grant period using an adapted Most Significant Change (MSC) approach.⁶ The MSC approach is an evaluation method that involves collecting change stories from the field and having a panel of designated interested parties select the most significant of these stories.⁶ While the team did not conduct all steps of the MSC approach, the adapted MSC approach allowed the T&E team to examine both intended and unintended impacts and helped provide an understanding on the values of different interested parties.

Table 3 displays information about the content of the bimonthly, midpoint and closeout, and follow-up surveys.

Table 3. Survey types, sections, and types of data collected

RP2 Survey	Section	Types of Data Collected
All bimonthly surveys*	Testing and Enrollment	# of tests performed # of positive tests Types of tests performed
	Challenges	Testing challenges Community engagement challenges
	Protocol Changes	Presence of protocol changes
	Self-Assessment	Self-assessment of enrollment and testing efficacy
Midpoint and Closeout surveys**	Update on Award	Costs to date Types of collaboration partners
	Project outcomes	Presence of TSBM benefits
	Impact of project award	Significant changes across the funding period
	Future Research Projects	Types of planned research products
	CDCC Support	CDCC support satisfaction
	Application and award process	Application and award process satisfaction
Follow-up survey*	Update on pilot award	Status update Progress made
	Project outcomes and impacts	Presence of new products after RP2 funding's conclusion
	Research products and partnerships	Update on research products
	RADx-UP support utility	Whether a project has used CDCC resources since the funding period ended or not Type of resources used

*Many projects 10/25 (40%) were granted extensions, and thus, had extended data collection timelines. Closeout data were collected beyond the 12-month mark.

** The midpoint and closeout surveys also include the sections in the bimonthly surveys, plus the additional items noted.

Data Analysis.

The T&E team analyzed survey data descriptively using Microsoft Power BI,⁸ a data analysis and visualization software. Count data are presented as cumulative when they were collected over multiple timepoints. For repeated measures of non-count data (i.e., satisfaction), we present the most recent timepoint. Text or qualitative data for the challenges, MSC, and TSBM sections were analyzed deductively using a rapid analysis approach with theory-based codebooks in Microsoft Excel. Most significant change data was not analyzed with a priori codes to allow for unexpected codes to emerge.

Results

B1. E01 - Evaluate funding success of the grant application and utilization process.

In total, there were **25 RP2 projects across seven funding cycles** (Cycle 1 n=8; Cycle 2 n=1; there were no funded projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4 n=4, Cycle 5 n=3, Cycle 6 n=3, and Cycle 7 n=6). **Table 4** presents metrics reflecting level of engagement with each funding cycle and start-up lead time following notification of funding.

Table 4. Application and Funding Implementation Measures per RP2 Funding Cycle

RP2 Project Cycle	Application Year	Number of Applicants	Number of Projects Awarded	Award Rate
Cycle 1	2021	9	8	88.8%
Cycle 2	2021	5	1	20.0%
Cycle 3	2021	0	0	-
Cycle 4	2021	8	4	50.0%
Cycle 5	2022	3	3	100%
Cycle 6	2022	7	3	43.0%
Cycle 7	2022-2023	11	6	55.0%
Total	2021-2023	43	25	58%

[^]The number reflects the average of three of the four awarded projects in the cycle. The fourth project was excluded because the average number of days between award notification and project initiation (160 days) was significantly longer than the other three projects due to unforeseen issues obtaining IRB approval.

B2. E02 - Evaluate Awardees' Satisfaction with CDCC Administration and Support Activities.

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support around completing the application process. The vast majority, **96.0%, of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the**

statements about receiving adequate support completing their application and easily understanding the Request for Application (RFA).

Figure 3: RP2 Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support Around Completing the Application (n=25)

Not Applicable responses were not included in the visual.

Satisfaction with the Support Provided by the RP2 Administration Team. All the respondents, **100%**, indicated they were satisfied or very satisfied with the cultural competency and responsiveness of the RP2 administration team. Most, **92.0%**, of respondents indicated that they were satisfied or very satisfied with the RP2 administration team’s knowledge in resolving project issues and onboarding and training resources. Finally, **96.0%** of respondents reported that they were satisfied or very satisfied with the RP2 administration’s response time to requests.

Figure 4. RP2 Project Satisfaction with Support Provided by Administration (n=24)

B3. E03 – Evaluate RP2 Program Reach and Diversity.

Geographic Diversity. RP2-funded projects **were spread throughout the US**, with the majority located in the South, Southwest, and West regions (see **Figure 5**). RP2 projects were most heavily concentrated in North Carolina, California, Texas, New Mexico, and Massachusetts,

although the six states with the highest number of cumulative COVID-19 cases (per 100,000) were Rhode Island, Alaska, Kentucky, North Dakota, and Tennessee.⁹

Figure 5. RP2 Project Geographic Diversity: Total Number of Rapid Pilot Projects by State (n= 25)

Figure developed by the American Institutes for Research (AIR) for RADx-UP

Institution Type. **Figure 6** reflects the institution type for award recipients, categorized based on criteria available from the National Center for Education Statistics.¹⁰ Seventeen funded projects were undertaken by non-minority-serving institutions (MSI), five by Hispanic-serving institutions, two projects (both in cycle 1) were led by Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving institutions (AANAPI), two projects (both in cycle 4) were led by Historically Black Colleges/Universities (HBCUs).

Figure 6. RP2 Project Institution Type (n= 25)

**Institution types are not mutually exclusive; MSI = Minority-serving institution; AANAPI=Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander; HBCU = Historically black colleges and universities; TCU = Tribal college and university*

Underserved Populations Reached. **Figure 7** provides a breakdown of underserved populations reached by RP2 projects, as reported by projects. The NIH has identified these eight underserved populations as being underrepresented in biomedical research and also being known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors.¹⁰ RP2 projects reached all eight NIH-designated underserved populations, demonstrating **broad reach among those prioritized by the program**. The majority of projects, **88.0%**, reached socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, followed closely with **75.0%** reaching Black populations, and **75.0%** reaching Hispanic/Latino populations.

Figure 7. Underserved Populations Reached by Projects (n=25)

Projects are not mutually exclusive. Projects can reach more than one underserved population.

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Reached. **Figure 8** displays the vulnerable communities reached by RP2 projects. COVID-19 vulnerable communities are populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19.¹¹ All populations considered COVID-19 vulnerable by the NIH were reached through RP2 projects. The three most reached groups were people with comorbidities, **75.0% of projects**, immigrants, and rural populations, both at **48.0% of projects**.

Figure 8. Vulnerable Communities Served by Projects (n=25)

Categories are not mutually exclusive. Projects can reach more than one COVID-19 vulnerable community.

Characteristics of RP2 Projects’ Partners. **Figure 9** reflects the number and type of organizations that projects partnered with to execute their work. The most common type of partner was community organizations/non-profits (**77 partnerships reported**) followed by academic institutions/universities (**15 partnerships reported**).

Figure 9. Characteristics of RP2 Projects’ Partners (n= 24)

Categories are not mutually exclusive. Projects could report multiple partner organizations.

B4. E04 – Evaluate Testing and Enrollment Outcomes.

The main aim of the RP2 program is to improve access to and uptake of novel and emerging diagnostic COVID-19 testing and testing strategies in underserved, medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations. Each project developed targets for enrolling participants who then received testing through the innovative methods and models being trialed. **Figure 10** shows enrollment relative to targets, on average, by cycle. Specifically, we calculated the percentage of a project’s target reached by dividing the total number for actual enrollment by cycle by the total targeted enrollment by cycle. Across all cycles, projects sought to enroll **11,810** participants and ultimately reached **53.9%** of this target (**6,363** participants enrolled) by the end of their project periods. However, there was variation across cycles. Two cycles exceeded their targeted enrollment, while four fell short of their targets, enrolling **20.8-52.9%** of what they predicted.

Figure 10. Percentage of Enrollment Targets Reached across all Cycles (n=20)

Five projects had not reported enrollment numbers at the time of this report. There were no funded projects in Cycle 3.

Figure 11 shows the percentage of testing targets reached across all cycles. This measure was calculated by dividing the total number of tests administered by cycle by the total projected number of tests by cycle. Across all cycles, **projects administered a total of 6,995 tests, 35.5% of the 19,709 projected**. Only one cycle (Cycle 6) exceeded their testing target.

Figure 11. Percentage of Testing Targets Reached by Cycle (n= 20)

Five projects had not reported testing numbers at the time of this report. No projects were funded in Cycle 3.

Challenges. Projects were asked about challenges at close-out, with the intent to capture persistent or overarching barriers to implementation across their award period. Fifteen projects responded to open-ended prompts around project challenges in their close-out survey, describing challenges that were coded into seven areas, across three broad categories: Operational Challenges, Technical Implementation Challenges, and Participation Challenges. **Table 5** lists these areas and provides definitions and illustrative quotes for each. **Figure 12** depicts the number of projects reporting each type of challenge. The majority of projects, **53.3%**, listed challenges with reporting testing results, **46.7%** reported administrative challenges, and a further **46.7%** reported challenges related to enrollment. Challenges with testing reporting were defined as challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients. Administrative challenges were defined as challenges with the release of funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, non-testing resource procurement. Enrollment challenges were defined as challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site had been established.

Figure 12. Type and Number of Challenges Reported by Projects (n=15)

Categories are not mutually exclusive. Projects could report more than one challenge

Table 5. Challenges Reported by Projects (n=15)

Theme	Code	Code Definition	Supporting quotes
Operational Challenges	Administrative	Release of funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, non-testing resource procurement	<i>"Limited research staff. Not enough budget to hire people and continue collecting samples as initially proposed."</i>
Technical Implementation Challenges	Testing Administration	Challenges identifying testing sites for administration of tests, administering test records	<i>"We experience challenges when the frequency of testing was done more than once a week. Adherence to the protocol was lower."</i>
	Testing Procurement	Challenges in obtaining tests to administer, including test kit identification, test kit selection, test availability	<i>"In Jan 2024, we experienced the longest delay because we collected samples and ran out of tests, so we had to wait for another batch to arrive for us to complete testing."</i>
	Testing reporting	Challenges in obtaining results from tests or reporting test results to patients	<i>"Many participants enrolled in the study but did not share the results of their self-test kits."</i>
Participation Challenges	Enrollment	Challenges/delays in recruiting subjects for research once a testing site has been established	<i>"During the time of the project, there were lower COVID rates so the demand for testing in the community was</i>

			<i>low. Community members had "COVID fatigue" by the time the study began so there was less of a demand for testing. Many community members were more interested in getting access to the vaccine than getting tested."</i>
	Partnerships	Challenges in working with community partners	<i>"There were more challenges to engage with local government which was usually overwhelmed with other problems once COVID-19 started to go down in number. We did not find sustained support after cases were going down."</i>

B5. E05 – Evaluate the Potential Translational Science Benefits of the RP2 Program.

To characterize the RP2 program’s potential translational science benefits, projects were asked in their midpoint and closeout surveys to list their project’s main impacts and for each impact listed, they were asked to indicate the area of the Translational Sciences Benefit Model with which it best aligned. Projects listed 65 distinct benefits. Project impacts **most commonly fell within the Community and Public Health impact area (42), followed by the Clinical impact area (16)** (see **Figure 13**). Examples of community and public health benefits reported included potential increased COVID-19 education, COVID-19 testing uptake, COVID-19 testing access, and COVID-19 community testing activities. These impacts were achieved through offering services in community clinics, telehealth appointments, and mobile clinics. For example, one project described how their activities “can inform and tailor educational resources for PEH [people experiencing homelessness] for COVID testing” suggesting a potential impact of increasing COVID-19 testing accessibility. Clinical impacts included increasing clinical services, reducing COVID-19 severity, increasing COVID-19 testing uptake, understanding COVID-19 trends, and creating innovative testing delivery options. Fewer projects reported economic (3) and policy (5) benefits. However, projects reported economic benefits including healthcare and hospitalization spending reductions and policy benefits including informing policies on COVID-19 positive testing reporting and vaccination in their closeout surveys.

Figure 13. RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the TSBM Domains (n= 25)

TSBM Indicators

Categories are not mutually exclusive. Impacts could be categorized into more than one Translational Science Benefit Domain.

Additional RADx-UP RP2 Project Outcomes. Beyond, but related to assessing potential TSBM benefits and significant changes as a result of their work (described below), projects were asked to report on other outcomes of the funding. They could select from the following categories: peer-reviewed publication; conference presentation; grant proposal; community event; patents, inventions, IP, etc.; partnership with testing vendor; other activity. A large majority of projects, **92.0%**, reported at least one additional outcome, with an average of **2.2** per project. Cycle 7 had the highest average number of outcomes per project at **2.4**. Developing a peer-reviewed publication was the most frequently reported outcome, with **22 peer-reviewed publications developed across all cycles**. Of the eighteen projects that had completed the follow-up survey, three indicated they had submitted a grant proposal since completion of their RP2 project.

Figure 14. Additional RP2 Project Outcomes (n= 23)

Not mutually exclusive. Projects could report more than one research product/outcome.

Most Significant Change as a Result of the RP2 Program. When completing the 12-month close-out and follow-up surveys, projects described what they felt was the most significant change to

have occurred due to their project funding. Projects primarily discussed increasing community collaborations or relationship building, followed by increasing COVID-19 education. One project reported:

“the most significant change for our community partners and our prospective cohort is that we know each other now and are connected, which is significant for marginalized groups that experience health disparities, economic distress and immigration stress. They know we've got their backs.”

This quote suggests that RP2 funding assisted in the creation of continued community connectedness that may persist beyond the completion of the project. Another reported that the funding allowed the team to expand:

“awareness about [the] pandemic and [to] provide information about the correct and timely treatment of infectious diseases in rural areas and in neighborhoods with fewer testing locations.”

This quote suggests that RP2 funding allowed the project to expand knowledge on infectious diseases in rural areas. The mention of infectious diseases may also indicate that increased education may apply to other infectious diseases as well as suggesting the potential for a lasting impact.

RADx-UP RP2 Project Sustainability. To assess project sustainability, RP2 projects were asked in the follow-up survey to describe efforts and progress towards extending research and activities beyond the official project period. Twelve (24.0%) RP2 projects that responded indicated plans to continue

“Our pop-ups provide the team with an opportunity to promote awareness of syndemic conditions impacting the community.” (Project 502)

“This pilot study has already been used as preliminary data to demonstrate engagement and funding. feasibility of data collection in the South Asian community for an RO1 that was submitted in February 2023.” (Project 141)

research and activities through manuscripts and reports, presenting findings at conferences, applying for additional grant funding, hosting community events, and partnering with testing vendors. Three quarters of respondents (8/12) indicated that they were working on publications making this the most frequently cited activity undertaken after program completion.

Key Takeaways and Conclusion

C1. General.

Through seven cycles, 25 RP2 funded projects advanced COVID-19 testing among underserved and vulnerable populations across the United States. Projects indicated high satisfaction with the support provided by the CDCC and RP2 support team. RP2 awards were mostly led by non-minority serving institutions. The evaluation found that awardees developed numerous

partnerships in support of their objectives, including with community-based/non-profit organizations, a stakeholder group that is typically less engaged in implementing research efforts. This finding highlights the importance of these types of organizations in increasing awareness and engagement of research projects, especially vital pilot projects like RP2 that have short lifecycles. These collaborative research partnerships, developed and strengthened through the RP2 awards, could contribute to a sustainable research infrastructure to the benefit of future research consortiums and further translation of RP2 generated insight into practice.

RP2 projects were most heavily concentrated in the US South, Southwest, and West regions indicating geographic diversity. However, at the state-level, the program did not have a presence in areas most heavily impacted by COVID-19. RP2 programs reached all underserved and vulnerable groups identified by the NIH as needing additional support and resources, demonstrating broad reach among populations standing to benefit from the program. In particular, projects focused on socioeconomically disadvantaged, Black and Hispanic/Latino communities, as well as people with comorbidities and immigrants. Many of these groups were among those experiencing the most severe disparities in COVID-19 morbidity and mortality, suggesting RP2 projects were well targeted to achieve intended health equity impacts.^{12, 13}

The ability of projects to meet their self-selected testing and enrollment targets varied across cycles. It is worth noting that the targets were developed by the projects themselves, so potentially targets set were overestimates or less attainable based upon the changing pandemic landscape (for example, widespread presence or discontinuation of organizational requirements for testing, vaccine development, variant surges, changing public attitudes and beliefs toward COVID-19 severity). Additionally, qualitative insights point to other potential contributors. For instance, administrative challenges (delays in receiving funding, delays in hiring) were a frequently reported challenge that could have contributed to projects' struggles to meet their testing and enrollment aims. These findings speak to the challenges of rapidly fielding short-cycle pilot projects in an emerging public health disaster. To successfully deploy this model in the future, projects may need more support to realize their full potential. Additional exploration of factors that enabled some cycles to exceed targets could provide important insight and enable future efforts to tactically and proactively provide needed supports.

Potential translational science impacts of the RP2 program were described largely in the areas of community or public health and clinical practice. When asked to report on and characterize their impact within TSBM domains, projects discussed having direct impacts on communities through increasing testing availability (e.g., mobile clinics) or building public understanding of the virus (e.g., adapting educational resources). Projects less frequently identified immediate impacts in economic or policy domains. Impacts were also measured by asking projects to reflect on what they felt was the most significant change to occur because of their work. Projects most often discussed building relationships, collaborating with communities, and

increasing public understanding of COVID-19 through education. These reflections also support the interpretation that projects were able to benefit communities/public health in the immediate term, while building potential for longer-term translational benefits. For instance, the community-academic partnerships formed may have facilitated community acceptance of testing during the project period and could also facilitate more rapid and streamlined deployment of effective strategies in a future emergency. Additionally, many projects invested in and produced peer-reviewed publications during and after the funding period, suggesting that insight from project activities will be disseminated more broadly within the scientific community which could lead to more downstream translational benefits across all TSBM domains.

C2 Lessons Learned and Project Feedback

Project Lessons Learned

Members of the RP2 Operations team met with project staff, including the Principal Investigator, to conduct a close-out meeting with each project. Close-out meetings discussed the project's aims and captured lessons learned about the project itself, along with feedback on the processes related to the program. The captured lessons learned have been summarized below. They highlight the importance of trust, incentives, and partnerships in successfully conducting testing and research.

- **COVID-19 Testing Methods:** Project feedback included highlighting the accuracy of PCR testing, which was crucial in early decision-making and community testing efforts. Home-based tests became more prominent later in the pandemic when they were more easily accessible. Testing fatigue was a common barrier expressed in later cycles of the program. Many projects expressed that community members no longer saw the need for continued testing, thus affecting enrollment numbers.
- **Testing Site Locations and Access:** Projects that utilized testing locations that were easily accessible and trusted by the community saw the greatest uptake. Mobile vans and vending machines were two novel approaches to expanding access. Participants reported greater trust when testing locations remained consistent and accessible when they needed them.
- **Incentives and Funding Limitations:** Incentives were crucial to testing and survey completion. Projects reported that incentivization was often limited by sponsor funding.
- **Infrastructure:** Many projects reported slow development and execution due to operational limitations associated with partners. For example, challenges were felt engaging schools and their leadership committees. Establishing partnerships early in the process was consistently expressed among projects.
- **Relationship with Community Partnerships:** Heavy emphasis was put on the need for strong relationships with community partners, local health departments, and

businesses. These partnerships were crucial for successful testing and isolation of positive cases. RP2 projects that reported the quickest execution of their projects often had well-established and strong existing relationships with their community partners. Those that developed their relationships throughout the program exhibited longer delays.

- **Language Barriers:** Many target populations (including asylum seekers and immigrants) faced challenges due to language barriers and fear of political repercussions. Providing educational materials, including fliers and videos, in multiple languages was crucial to update and overall trust.
- **Educational Materials:** Some of the most consistent feedback received was related to the use of multiple forms of media to educate participants. Videos were an especially impactful method for educating the community and facilitating self-testing. Other novel media included comic strips depicting the importance of testing and multi-lingual fliers.
- **Summary of Themes:** Project close out feedback emphasized the importance of trust, community engagement, and proper incentives, suggesting these lessons can serve as a blueprint for future pandemics.

Program Lessons Learned

The information below collected from projects discusses experiences and feedback related to the CDCC support and NIH grant processes, highlighting both positive and negative aspects.

- **NIH Guidance:** Concerns were raised about the NIH changing messages regarding FDA-approved tests and guidance, which negatively impacted projects.
- **NIH Infrastructure:** Proper infrastructure ahead of a program's initiation is paramount to success. Many RP2 projects had to create their own infrastructure from the ground up, thus making the completion of a 12-month project difficult. Projects also expressed difficulty developing the relevant surveys to capture the required CDEs. Simply having a copy of the codebook was not sufficient and many projects wish there was additional assistance setting up their surveys ahead of enrollment and testing.
- **Challenges and recommendations:** Program challenges included short timelines, difficulties with data upload and REDCap's offline capabilities, and the extensive scope of analysis. Recommendations included better initial use of resources, clearer access to the codebook, and more NIH support for community research education.
- **Positive aspects of grant processes:** The grant submission process was described as easy, and the RP2 application expedited awards. The Partnering for Impact Program (P4I) and CDCC-facilitated meetings were highlighted as important for collaboration and

support. The interaction between Principal Investigators (PIs) and the CDCC was considered successful and supportive.

Program Benefit

The RP2 program was highly impactful. First, the program accomplished its mandate to improve access to innovations in COVID-19 diagnostic testing and testing strategies in underserved communities. The program was far-reaching, involving a wide spectrum of socio-economic, geographic, and ethnic vulnerable populations across 18 US states and territories (Figures 5, 7-8). Through research implementation, the program demonstrated it is not only feasible, but often necessary, to deploy innovative strategies such as population-specific incentives, and use of crowdsourcing, mobile clinics, video clips, and smartphone testing, to reduce barriers to diagnostic testing and testing uptake.

Second, the program increased our understanding of the barriers associated with the lack of access or inhibiting uptake of underserved communities to novel testing and testing technologies. While cultural barriers exist, trust in institutions and government is a common challenge across underserved populations and a strong indicator of testing success and uptake. Thus, community engagement is not only necessary, but the strength of the relationships in the community or population is critical. Buy-in from the community and community leaders is important, but the most successful projects enlisted local businesses such barber shops, church groups, and community volunteers to participate in the research study (Figures 10-11). Other key barriers identified included literacy level, language barriers, travel distance, and technology barriers, such as internet or smartphone access.

Third, the program supported the infrastructure and expertise necessary to stand up and implement a pilot research program at national scale for rapid response to a pandemic emergency. The diverse scientific and technical expertise of the Testing Core and the administrative and operational expertise of the RP2 team were essential not only to successfully initiate the program but also to make critical interpretations and decisions rapidly throughout the changing landscape of pandemic (surges) and national challenges including changes to federal policies (NIH, CDC, FDA) and national supply chain shortages. The RP2 team built protocols, procedures, and established standards as well compiled the collective know-how and lessons-learned that altogether comprise the program's operational infrastructure that can be adapted for fast (re)deployment when the need arises for future national or pandemic emergencies.

While the program's infrastructure is an important legacy of the RP2 program, other key benefits or return on investment (ROI) of the program with sustained or lasting effect are summarized in the figure below.

BY THE NUMBERS

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Projects at a Glance

Collected in the RADx-UP Publications Dashboard as of May, 2025

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model

Rapid Research Pilots Evaluation Logic Model

